

ASSESSING MARMA CHIKITSA EFFECTIVENESS IN MANAGING KNEE PAIN - A CASE STUDY

Dr. Suryanath Yogi^{1*}, Dr. Rita Marwaha², Dr. Pankaj Gupta³

^{1*}Pt. Khushilal Sharma Govt. (Auto.) Ayurveda College and Institute Bhopal (M.P.) India.

²Professor & HOD, PG Department of Rachna Sharir, Pt. Khushilal Sharma Govt. (Auto.) Ayurveda College and Institute Bhopal (M.P.) India.

³Professor, PG Department of Rachna Sharir, Pt. Khushilal Sharma Govt. (Auto.) Ayurveda College and Institute Bhopal (M.P.) India.

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*Corresponding Author

Dr. Suryanath Yogi

Pt. Khushilal Sharma Govt.
(Auto.) Ayurveda College
and Institute Bhopal (M.P.)
India.

ABSTRACT

Osteoarthritis (OA) is a widespread degenerative joint condition affecting people globally, caused by wear and tear and gradual loss of cartilage. Common symptoms of Osteoarthritis of knee include pain, stiffness, swelling, and reduced mobility. Marma Science is an ancient medical discipline that prevents and treats diseases, promotes health and mental calmness, and fosters self-healing. Marma Chikitsa involves gentle stimulation of Marma points. This study assesses Marma Chikitsa effect on pain management of knee osteoarthritis. A 48-year-old male farmer with bilateral knee osteoarthritis received Marma Chikitsa for 21 days. Daily progress was recorded. After 21 days, the patient experienced significant relief, with approximately 70-80% of symptoms alleviated and improved quality of life. Marma Chikitsa, a non-pharmacological treatment, provides substantial relief

for knee osteoarthritis management.

KEYWORDS: Ayurveda, Marma, Osteoarthritis, Marma Chikitsa.

INTRODUCTION

Osteoarthritis also called degenerative joint disorder, is the most common types of joint disorder and is one of the most disabling conditions in developed nations. It is characterized by the progressive diminution of articular cartilage. The disease most commonly affects the joints in the knees, hands, feet, and spine and is related to ageing. Patient with primary

disease are usually asymptomatic until they are in their fifties.^[1] The most common affected joint is knee joint. It is also known as degenerative joint disease of the knee, which typically occurs as the result of wear and tear along with progressive loss of articular cartilage. It can be categorised as primary osteoarthritis and secondary osteoarthritis.^[2] There are around 8.7 million individuals (20 years and older) with incident knee OA in 2020 worldwide.^[3] In India, prevalence is found to be 28.7% and it is more prevalent in females (31.6%) than in males (28.1%).^[4] Knee osteoarthritis often presents with gradual-onset pain, swelling and stiffness, worsening with activity or inactivity. Advanced cases can lead to persistent pain, interfering with daily life and causing substantial functional impairment. Under the guidelines of the International Association of Osteoarthritis, conservative treatment is preferred for knee osteoarthritis. Conservative treatments include physical therapies, such as weight loss and exercise and drugs, such as non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) and propranolol.^[5] Single agents are not optimal in improving pain and function in knee osteoarthritis patients. Drugs, such as NSAIDs, are not effective, and may even have adverse effects on the cardiovascular system, stomach and kidneys, and thus their use has to be limited in elderly knee osteoarthritis patients.^[6] Marma therapy offers a new hope for treating the disease, providing prompt relief through a non-pharmacological approach.

CASE REPORT

The patient was a 51-year old male and is a teacher by profession. Patient gradually developed pain and swelling in unilateral knee. Pain is aggravated by walking and climbing stairs and relieved by rest. He took allopathic analgesics and got some symptomatic relief but symptoms aggravated since past 7 months.

CHIEF COMPLAINTS

- Pain and swelling in unilateral knee
- Tenderness
- Crepitation
- Restriction of movement.

HISTORY

PAST MEDICAL HISTORY – No history of Hypertension and Diabetes mellitus.

FAMILY HISTORY - Father has a history of Arthritis and Hypertension.

PERSONAL HISTORY

1. Appetite - Normal
2. Bowel - Clear
3. Sleep - Disturbed
4. Micturition – Normal.

PHYSICAL EXAMINATION

1. Body weight - 78 kg
2. Heart rate - 88/min
3. Respiration rate - 20/min
4. Blood pressure - 130/80 mm Hg.

ON EXAMINATION

1. Duration of pain - 7 month
2. Site - unilateral
3. Location - Right knee joint pain
4. Pain - severe in nature (grade - 3)
5. Swelling - severe (grade - 3)
6. Stiffness - present, for 10-15 min (grade - 3)
7. Restricted movements - does not allow passive movements (grade – 3)
8. VAS scale range between 4-6
9. Crepitus - audible (grade - 3).

INVESTIGATIONS

1. X Ray
2. CBC with ESR

DIAGNOSIS

Osteoarthritis (OA) of knee.

TREATMENT PROTOCOL

Treatment involved administration of *Marma* Chikitsa. Present study includes stimulation of 4 *Marma* that is *Indrabasti Marma*, *Gulpha Marma*, *Janu Marma*, *Talhridaya Marma* These will be stimulated for 15-18 times on an average in single sitting.^[7]

Total duration - 21 days

Follow up - 7th day

S.NO.	MARMA	STIMULATION TIME	FREQUENCY	DURATION
1.	INDRABASTI MARMA	0.8 SEC	15-18 TIMES	ONCE A DAY
2.	GULPHA MARMA	0.8 SEC	15-18 TIMES	ONCE A DAY
3.	JANU MARMA	0.8 SEC	15-18 TIMES	ONCE A DAY
4.	TALHIRDAYA MARMA	0.8 SEC	15-18 TIMES	ONCE A DAY

- A steady and moderate pressure is applied slowly and gently at the Marma points.
- Pressure was increased gradually depending upon patient strength.

TALHIRDAYA MARMA

GULPHA MARMA

JANU MARMA

INDRABASTI MARMA

Assessment Criteria

1. Pain

SN	Criteria	Grading
1.	No pain	0
2.	Mild pain	1

3.	Moderate pain without difficulty in walking	2
4.	Moderate pain with difficulty in walking	3
5.	Severe pain with difficulty in walking	4

2. Swelling

S.N.	Criteria	Grading
1.	No swelling	0
2.	Slightly obvious	1
3.	Covers well over the bony prominence	2
4.	Marked and much elevated	3
5.	Severe and very much elevated	4

3. Stiffness

S.N.	Criteria	Grading
1.	No stiffness	0
2.	<5 min	1
3.	5-10 min	2
4.	10-15 min	3
5.	>15 min	4

4. Crepitus

S.N.	Criteria	Grading
1.	No crepitus	0
2.	Occasional crepitus	1
3.	Persistent and palpable crepitus	2
4.	Persistent and audible crepitus	3

5. Restricted Movement

S.N.	Criteria	Grading
1.	No pain	0
2.	Pain without winching of face	1
3.	Pain with winching of face	2
4.	Prevent complete flexion	3
5.	Does not allow passive movement	4

6. VAS Scale

S. No.	Pain	Grade
1	VAS range in between 0-2	0
2	VAS range in between 2-4	1
3	VAS range in between 4-6	2
4	VAS range in between 6-8	3
5	VAS range in between 8-10	4

OBSERVATION

After completion of 21 days of Marma chikitsa there is significant changes in all parameters.

Which are mentioned below:

Pain – Decreased (grade -1)

Swelling - Decreased (grade -1)

Stiffness - Decreased (grade -1)

VAS score – 2-4

Restriction of movement - Decreased (grade -1)

Diagnostic criteria	Before treatment	After treatment
Pain	3	1
Swelling	3	1
Stiffness	3	1
Crepitus	3	1
Restricted movement	3	1
VAS scale	4-6	2-4

DISCUSSION

In Ayurveda, osteoarthritis can be correlated to Sandhigatavata, where vitiated Vata dosha localizes in the joints (sandhi), causing symptoms like pain (vedana), swelling (sopha), and limited mobility. Most of our understanding of osteoarthritis comes from observational studies, with diagnosis relying on clinical findings. As a significant public health issue, osteoarthritis burden will escalate with the aging population. Currently, treatments are not curative, often requiring joint replacement surgery for many patients.

As *Marmas* are the seats of *Prana*, the vital life force that governs the physical and subtle processes of the body, the stimulation of *Marmas* can alter the state of *Prana* at these locations, causing a corresponding effect on the physical and subtle processes, and the flow of energy.^[8]

Therefore, by the proper stimulation of *Marmas*, the *Prana* can be modulated in such a way that it can be used to remove blockages, and decrease or enhance the physical and subtle energy currents within the body, resulting in the corresponding healing effect. Since *Prana* is connected to *Vata Dosha*, whose vitiation leads to the maximum types of diseases, hence *Marma Therapy* can be especially useful in treating the *Vata* disorders, which correspond to chronic degenerative diseases.^[9] *Marma Chikitsa* provided prompt relief from pain and stiffness, improved joint mobility, and strengthened knee structures. While not a complete cure, it showed significant benefits in pain management, offering a new approach to addressing osteoarthritis.

CONCLUSION

Marma Chikitsa is usually performed to relieve joint pain, restore joint movements and to correct the deformity. This case study highlights Marma Chikitsa potential effectiveness in managing knee osteoarthritis pain, demonstrating significant pain relief and improved mobility without adverse effects. It offers a promising non-invasive, non-pharmacological alternative for knee osteoarthritis treatment.

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